

THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY ALIGNED CARBON NANOFIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES BY USING AC ELECTRICAL FIELD

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SUMMARY

Unidirectionally aligned carbon nanofiber/epoxy composites were fabricated by using AC electrical field. Three types of carbon nanofibers were used. Thermal and electrical conductivities in the aligned direction were measured and three point bending tests were conducted to investigate the effect of alignment on the mechanical properties.

Keywords: Carbon nanofiber, Alignment, AC electrical field, Thermal conductivity, Electrical conductivity, Mechanical property

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that carbon nanofibers (CNFs) enhance stiffness, electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity of polymers [1]. Alignment of carbon nanofibers in polymers is expected to increase the performances in the aligned direction. Application of alternating electric (AC) field to uncured epoxy including CNFs may cause alignment of CNFs in the electric field direction, and thus unidirectionally aligned CNF/Epoxy composites can be fabricated [2, 3]. In this study, three types of CNF were used to investigate the effect of the type of CNF on material properties. At first, unidirectionally aligned CNF/Epoxy composites were observed by using an optical microscope. As a result, it is found that upper limitation of the weight fraction to align CNFs varies with the type of CNF. Furthermore, thermal and electrical conductivities in the through-thickness direction were measured for various weight fractions of each CNF. Experiment results show that alignment enhances the thermal and electrical conductive properties and the type of the CNF affects these conductive properties. Three-point bending test were conducted to investigate the effect of the alignment on the mechanical properties.

MATERIALS

Cup-stacked type carbon nanotube (CSCNT, GSI Creos Corp.) and two types of vapor grown carbon fibers with different diameters (VGCF and VGCF-S, Showa Denko K.K.) were used as filler and room temperature cured epoxy (General Purpose Epoxy Resin/Hardener #3, System Three Resins, Inc.) was used as resin. CSCNT is composed

of truncated conical graphene sheets. The truncated conical graphene sheets are stacked. Thus, CSCNT has a large hollow core and open ends. VGCF and VGCF-S are kinds of MWCNT, and the diameters are 150 nm and 100 nm, respectively. Table 1 shows the physical properties of the three types of CNF.

Table 1 Physical properties of CNFs.

		CSCNT	VGCF	VGCF-S
Diameter	[nm]	50~200	150	100
Length	[mm]	20	10	9
Resistivity	[W·m]	5.5×10^{-7}	1×10^{-6}	1×10^{-6}
Thermal conductivity	[W/mK]	—	1200	1200

The epoxy resin consists of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A >70 % and alkylglycidyl ether <30 %, and the curing agent consists of modified aliphatic amines 50-70 % and nonyl phenol 30-50 %. The epoxy resin cures at room temperature, and the working time at 25 °C is 60 min. The viscosities of epoxy and curing agent are 550 mPa·s and 350 mPa·s, respectively.

MECHANISM OF ALIGNMENT

Figure 1 shows possible mechanisms to align CNFs and to form chain-like networks under AC electrical field. As soon as applying AC electrical field to CNF suspension, each CNF is polarized due to electrostatic induction. AC electrical field makes each CNF align in the electric field direction because of the rotational moment induced by the polarization. The polarization also causes agglomeration due to electrostatic force between CNFs. These mechanisms result in the formation of unidirectionally aligned chain-like network of CNFs.

In the case of applying direct current (DC) electrical field, the unidirectional alignment of CNFs does not occur because CNFs are electrified in the suspension and thus migrate to one electrode [4, 5].

Fig.1 Alignment and formation of network structure of CNFs.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fabrication of Specimen

In order to disperse CNFs in the epoxy resin, CNFs and epoxy resin (without curing agent) were mixed by using the planetary mixer for 20 min. This suspension was sonicated for 1 hr and then mixed with the curing agent by using a planetary mixer for 20 min again. This suspension was poured into a mold that is composed of a couple of copper plates coated by insulating polymer (polyvinyl alcohol) and a silicon rubber dam (110 x 110 mm). Epoxy was cured for 6 hr at 50 °C with 800 V/cm of AC square-wave electrical field at 10 Hz (Fig.2).

Fig.2 Schematic of specimen molding.

In order to confirm the microstructures of composites with AC electrical field during fabrication, thin pieces were sliced for optical microscopic observation. The micrographs of the microstructures for various weight fractions of three types of CNFs were shown in Figs.3 - 5, respectively. In the case of 0.5 wt% and 1.0 wt% of CSCNT, alignment and network formation of CSCNTs was observed parallel to the AC electrical field. For 1.5 wt% and 2.0 wt%, CSCNTs did not seem to align. In the case of 0.5 wt% of VGCF, alignment and network formation was observed. For 1.0 wt% and above, VGCFs did not seem to align. In the case of 0.2 wt% of VGCF-S, alignment and network formation was observed partly. For 0.5 wt% and above, VGCF-Ss did not seem to align.

(a) 0.5 wt%

(b) 1.0 wt%

(c) 1.5 wt%

(d) 2.0 wt%

Fig.3 Micrographs of CSCNT/Epoxy composites.

(a) 0.5 wt%

(b) 1.0 wt%

Fig.4 Micrographs of VGCF/Epoxy composites.

(a) 0.2 wt%

(b) 0.5 wt%

Fig.5 Micrographs of VGCF-S/Epoxy composite.

In polymer composites containing conductive fillers such as CNF, it is well known that the electrical conductivity of the composites exhibits percolation behavior [1]. In order to polarize each CNF by applying AC electrical field, the weight fraction of CNF should

be less than the percolation threshold. Figures 3 - 5 show that unidirectionally aligned chain-like networks of CSCNT were formed at higher filler weight contents because CSCNT has good dispersibility and the higher percolation threshold than those of VGCF and VGCF-S. On the other hand, it was difficult for VGCF-S to form a unidirectionally aligned network even at low filler weight-content. This is because VGCF-S is easy to agglomerate due to its high aspect ratio and the percolation threshold is much lower.

Thermal Conductivity

Specimens (30 mm x 30 mm) were cut from each CNF/Epoxy composite plate and the resin rich region of the surface was removed by sand paper. Thermal conductivity in the through-thickness direction was measured by using the steady-state heat conduction method. The specimens with 1 mm and 2 mm thick were prepared to eliminate contact thermal resistances between specimen and sensors. Figure 6 shows the measurement results of CSCNT/Epoxy composites, and Fig.7 shows the results of VGCF/Epoxy and VGCF-S/Epoxy composites. The vertical axis is the thermal conductivity and the horizontal axis is the weight fraction of CNF in each figure. The scatter band was determined by 5 % of significance probability. In Fig.6, there was no significant difference of thermal conductivities between specimens with AC electrical field and without AC electrical field. Since CSCNT has unconnected structure in the longitudinal direction, its thermal conductivity is low and thus the contribution of filler to improve thermal conductivity is low. Therefore, it was not evident whether alignment of CNF enhances thermal conductivity for CSCNT. In Fig.7, enhancement of the thermal conductivity was clearly observed. That means applying AC electrical field enhances the thermal conductivity of the specimens.

Fig.6 Thermal conductivity of CSCNT/Epoxy composites.

Fig.7 Thermal conductivity of VGCF/Epoxy and VGCF-S/Epoxy composites.

Electrical Conductivity

Upper and lower surfaces of the specimens used for measuring thermal conductivity were coated by silver paste and lead wires were attached to measure DC electrical resistance. The measurement results were shown in Fig.8. The vertical axis is the electrical resistivity and the horizontal axis is the weight fraction of CNFs. In CSCNT/Epoxy composite, the electrical resistances were not measurable for all specimens of 0.5 wt% and several specimens of 1.0 wt% without AC electrical field because of their very high resistivity. On the other hand, electrical conduction appeared for specimens with CSCNT of 0.5 wt% and 1.0 wt% to which AC electrical field was applied during fabrication. That is because many conductive paths were formed by AC electrical field. In VGCF/Epoxy composite, the electrical resistance of all specimens of 0.5 wt% without AC electrical field was not measurable, while electrical conduction appeared in all specimens of 0.5 wt%. Although alignment of VGCF was not clearly observed at 1.0wt% and above, the electrical resistivities of the specimens with AC electrical field were lower than those of the specimens without AC electrical field because conductive paths were formed partly by AC electrical field at the regions with low filler content and near the electrodes. In VGCF-S/Epoxy composite with 0.2 wt%, electrical conduction appeared in all specimens regardless of AC electrical field, and the resistivities of the specimens with AC electrical field were lower than that of the specimens without AC electrical field. For 0.5 wt%, the resistivities did not depend on AC electrical field.

Fig.8 Resistivity of CNF/Epoxy composites.

Three Point Bending Test

Three point bending tests were conducted to investigate the effect of alignment on the mechanical properties. The aligned direction is in the through-thickness direction as shown in Fig.9. Figure 10 shows the load-displacement curves for epoxy, randomly oriented and unidirectionally oriented specimens. The results indicate that alignment affects the bending modulus and strength. In the case of bending, vertical alignment as shown in Fig.9 does not contribute to the reinforcement. Thus, the bending modulus and strength of unidirectionally aligned specimens are lower than those of randomly oriented specimens.

Fig.9 Three point bending test

Fig.10 Flexural stress-strain curves.

CONCLUSIONS

Three types of unidirectionally aligned CNF/Epoxy composites were fabricated under AC electrical field, and the electrical and thermal conductivities were measured. As a result, it was found that upper limitation of the weight fraction to align CNFs varies with the types of CNF. Alignment enhances the thermal and electrical conductive properties and the type of CNF affects these conductive properties. Alignment also affects the mechanical properties.

References

1. E.T. Thostenson, Z. Ren, and T.W. Chou, "Advances in the science and technology of carbon nanotubes and their composites", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol.61, pp.1899-1912 (2001).
2. T. Prasse, J-Y. Cavallé and W. Bauhofer, "Electric anisotropy of carbon nanofibre/epoxy resin composites due to electric field induced alignment", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol.63, pp.1835-1841 (2003)
3. Y. Shimamura, T. Chiba, K. Tohgo, H. Araki and S. Ishiwata, "Conductive Properties of Unidirectionally Aligned Carbon Nanofiber/Epoxy composite", *Proc. 10th Japan International SAMPE Symposium*, pp.(NC1-4)-1 - (NC1-4)-6, (2007), Tokyo, Japan.
4. K. Yamamoto, S. Akita and Y. Nakayama, "Orientation of carbon nanotubes using electrophoresis", *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* Vol.35, pp.L917-L918 (1996).
5. N. Koratkar, A. Modi, J. Kim, B. Q. Wei, R. Vajtai, S. Talapatra and P. M. Ajayan, "Mobility of carbon nanotubes in high electric field", *J. Nanosci. Nanotech.*, Vol.4, No.1/2, pp.69-71 (2004).